

EXPRESSION OF THE IMAGE OF THE BUTTERFLY IN POETRY

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Abstract: this article talks about one of the representatives of the world of fauna - the image of a butterfly. In expressing the artistic landscape of the world, in revealing different aspects of the human image, artists actively use living creatures belonging to the group of animals and insects, among other images. The article expresses an opinion about the genesis of the image of a butterfly, the types of meaning expressed by its first roots. In modern poetry, the role of the image of the butterfly in the composition of the work, its importance, symbolic expressions are explained by giving examples of a number of poetic fragments.

Keywords: human image, artistic way of thinking, landscape of the artistic world, image of a butterfly, folklore, modern Uzbek poetry, Muhammad Yusuf

INTRODUCTION. In works of art, in addition to the image of a person, we often see the image of animals, insects, birds, and plants. They are used to widely express a person's personality, his spiritual and spiritual world. The introduction of the world of animals and plants into the work increases the potential of this work. Literary scholar Nomon Rahimjonov gives the following opinion in this regard: "Fairy tales, legends, myths and narratives, which are widely used in artistic and aesthetic thinking, encourage us to know the Universe. The speech of animals (deer, wolf, fox, sheep, etc.), insects (such as ants, butterflies, dragonflies), the speaking of mountains, rocks, trees, crane-eyed springs, and seas is an attempt to express Being and Non-existence, Man. The purpose of this kind of Zikr is to remember Allah, to adorn the hearts with the name of Allah" [1, 3].

Therefore, in expressing the artistic landscape of the universe, in understanding its essence, in reflecting the entire beauty of the Creator, in feeling the unique existence of Biru, the world of animals and creatures, in addition to the image of man, participated equally.

MAIN PART. Butterflies are one of the brilliant images used in Uzbek poetry since ancient times. Butterflies are one of nature's most beautiful insects and are sure to inspire a lot of interest in anyone who encounters them. These little creatures were often seen as symbols of freedom and beauty.

The genesis of the image of the butterfly goes back thousands of years. In many cultures, butterflies are interpreted in connection with the spiritual world and the material world. According to some beliefs, butterflies, especially white butterflies, are messengers between the universe and a spiritual being. In this context, seeing a white butterfly was interpreted as a visit or message from deceased loved ones. These creatures are believed to carry with them the souls of those who have crossed over to the other side.

For some people, seeing a white butterfly can be comforting and have spiritual significance, as they feel like they are being visited by a loved one or as a sign of the afterlife. There is a scientific basis for the belief that this means that those we have lost will never leave us completely and that their love and energy will continue to surround us.

In some folklore beliefs, white butterflies are spiritual protectors and guides. It is believed that these beings can help us in times of need and guide us in times of confusion. Seeing a white butterfly can be interpreted as a reminder that we are being cared for and protected by unseen forces.

We find the first roots of the image of the butterfly in folklore works. In the song "Butterfly", which is part of children's songs, the image of a butterfly is embodied in the form of an innocent, beautiful creature:

Kapalagim kapalak,
Buncha go'zal bo'lmasang.
Qanotlaring rang-barang
Buncha maftun etmasang.
Osmonda uchib yursang,
Ko'zlarim senda bo'lar.
Kapalagim kapalak,

Mening qalbim shod aylar.
Kapalagim kapalak,
Kel birga biz o'ynaylik.
Sen uchgin men ortingdan
Quvnoq bo'lib chopayin.
Kapalagim qanoting
Qayrilmasin hechqachon
Sening go'zal surating
Kitobimda allaqachon.

Children will love to spend time with this strange looking creature and play catch with it. The song was written in the language of a child and appeared in the form of an appeal to a butterfly. It is about her external beauty, strong spiritual charm that captivates not only children, but also any person. But all these definitions are important because they are expressed in a simple style typical of children.

When we look at modern Uzbek poetry, we come across the butterfly again and again in the composition of the images that appear in it. So, the tradition of using this image, the way of creative approach, has not lost its power yet. We can witness the rise of the butterfly to the level of a symbol in the lyrics of some artists. This can be proved by the example of the poems of the national poet of Uzbekistan Muhammad Yusuf. For example, in his poem "Sevgi bamisoli lalakizgaldok ..." which is a part of the "Love Ship" poetic series, the image of a butterfly is not just an insect, but a friend and companion of a person.

Sevgi bamisoli lolaqizg'aldoq,
Teginmay bo'lmaydi,
Tegsang to'kilar.

Alvon bir gumbazning o'rtasi oppoq...

Buni bir menu bir kapalak bilar.

Men o'sha gumbazga boshimni suqdim

– Qizil ko'ylakli bir qizgina kular.

Bunday boqma menga: uqdingmi?

Uqdim...

Buni bir menu bir kapalak bilar [2,4].

The poem combines the three beautiful things in life. It is not difficult for the poet Zucco to understand the essence. These are: love, tulips and butterflies. The life

of all three depends on his charm. From the outside, it is beautiful and soulful. It has the power to bewitch at a glance. If you don't react carefully, it will turn into a mess in an instant. In the verses, Svgi is compared to Lolaqiggaldok. "The center of an alvan dome is white..." - this is a joke. The two are so attractive that you won't even know you're accidentally touching them, man. But as soon as we touch it, it starts to expire. A hint is also hidden in the words of the lyrical hero that the butterfly understands this situation well. Because the life of a butterfly is so short that it sheds if you touch it. The lyrical basis of this can be seen in the next verse:

So'ng u oqqanotim uchdiyu ketdi,
Uning umri bir kun – choshgohda o'lar.
Momo Yer aylanib manzilga yetdi,
Buni bir menu bir charxpalak bilar... [2, 4]

In fact, the poet's life span is one day - until choshgah. Eve's life ends when she reaches her destination by turning around the Earth. A poet and a poet know this with a strong feeling. In this place, Charkhpalak represented such units as destiny, life, world, and time.

In the poem that begins with the lines "There are strangers like me who cannot be seen..." from Muhammad Yusuf's collection of poems "Ishq Kemasi", the butterfly embodies the image of humble, humble people who do not hurt anyone:

Menday g'aribni ham ko'rolmaslar bor
Nurab borarmanu o'zim shunday ham,
Tugab borarmanu o'zim shunday ham,
Ko'ksimga tosh otmay yurolmaslar bor...
Tovushim chiqmas bir kapalakcha ham,
Sadosiz kuzatgim kelar dunyoni.

Ko'tarolmas hatto temir tokcha ham

Ular qanotimga ortgan riyoni [2, 206].

There is probably no animal in the world as beautiful as a butterfly, and at the same time harmless. The poet points to this and says, "Not even a butterfly makes a sound." He looks like a strange butterfly that observes the world silently, without making a single sound. That is, the lyrical hero, who lives without touching anyone, without trying to reveal his existence, without making a sound, like this little creature, knows only beauty and never sees evil in anyone. He does not even think of hurting those around him. Unfortunately, even in this situation, those around him

do not leave him alone and do not allow him to feel pleasure. The lyrical hero complains that they cannot bear the weight of the riya on their wings as thin as the wings of a butterfly, even an iron rack.

Tunda she'r aytishdik kapalak bilan,
Yalpizni alqadim,
Gulni alqadim.
Yonimga sudralib kelib bir ilon
Ko'zoynak ostidan boqdi.
Payqadim.
Quvdi yolg'iz o'shal hamxonamni u.
Quvdi parilarni quvgan kabi dev.
Hurkitib yuborib parvonamni u
Bo'ynimga o'ralib oldi:
Meni sev!.. [3, 19-20]

In this poem, taken from the book "Erka kiyik", beginning with the lines "At night we wrote a poem with a butterfly...", the butterfly is depicted as a roommate, lover, companion of the lyrical hero. In contrast to this image, the image of a snake is represented in the poem as a symbol of a man who wants evil and is forced to love himself. Putting these two images in conflict with each other laid the groundwork for revealing the essence of the image of a butterfly. The poem is based on symbols from head to toe, and it can be explained based on scientific evidence that it enriches the world of thought of the poets and is an artistic tool in their understanding of the landscape of the artistic world.

CONCLUSION. In order to fully understand and understand the whole existence, and of course to give its explanation, the tools that stand along with the human image in the works of art are the representatives of the world of nature and animals. We cannot imagine our life without them. In order to understand the essence of the phenomena and processes occurring in existence, we need to see the nature, animals and civilization that surround us in a perfect unity. Animals and plants depicted in works of art are the main tool for detailing the image of a person. We see a clear proof of this in the example of Uzbek poetry.

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